

Telomerase Activity and Regenerative Capacity in *Hydra vulgaris*.

Valeria Russo, Ion Udroi, Antonella Sgura and Marco Colasanti*

Department of Science, University "ROMA TRE", 00146 Rome, Italy

*e-mail: marco.colasanti@uniroma3.it

Abstract

Hydra vulgaris represents one of the most important model organism for studying aging and regeneration due to its apparent biological immortality and high regenerative capacity. This preliminary study investigated telomerase activity in *H. vulgaris* specimens subjected to repeated cutting procedures and examined the effects of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), a known telomerase inhibitor, on telomerase activity and regenerative capacity. Using the telomeric repeat amplification protocol (TRAP) assay, we documented intense telomerase activity in untreated polyps following regeneration. EGCG treatment significantly reduced telomerase activity and correlated with decreased regenerative rates, suggesting a link between telomerase suppression and senescence induction in this organism.

Introduction

The mechanisms underlying cellular aging and senescence remain fundamental questions in developmental and evolutionary biology. While aging is characteristic of most metazoans, *Hydra vulgaris* represents an exceptional organism that exhibits apparent biological immortality and remarkable regenerative capacity [1]. This cnidarian has emerged as a critical model system for investigating the cellular and molecular basis of aging, particularly because it possesses high concentrations of stem cells and can completely regenerate its body structures [2]. The apparent lack of senescence in *H. vulgaris* provides a unique opportunity to examine how continuous proliferation and regeneration are maintained at the molecular level. Telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT), a ribonucleoprotein enzyme responsible for maintaining telomeric DNA sequences, is hypothesized to play a crucial role in cellular immortality. In mammals, TERT activity is typically repressed in somatic cells but remains active in germ and stem cells [3]. A few studies have demonstrated the presence of the gene encoding TERT in *Hydra vulgaris* [4,5]. Understanding telomerase dynamics in organisms with sustained regenerative capacity may illuminate the fundamental mechanisms of aging and cellular renewal.

Methods

Hydra vulgaris specimens were maintained in culture medium at 17 °C under controlled lighting conditions. Three experimental groups were established: untreated uncut controls, untreated cut specimens subjected to repeated bisection at four-to five-day intervals, and specimens treated with EGCG (10 µg/ml) concurrent with cutting procedures. The specimens were monitored daily for morphological changes and regenerative capacity over a seven-week period. Telomerase activity was assessed using the real-time quantitative telomerase repeat amplification protocol (RQ-TRAP) assay with protein extracts standardized to 1 µg per sample. All experiments were conducted in biological triplicates with appropriate statistical analysis.

Results and Discussion

Our findings revealed intense basal telomerase activity in *H. vulgaris*, with activity levels markedly increased by approximately 1.6-fold in cut specimens compared to uncut controls after seven weeks of treatment (Fig. 1). The TRAP assay confirmed the specificity of telomerase activity, demonstrating a clear signal distinguishing telomerase-positive *Hydra* extracts from background control reactions.

When the cut specimens were co-incubated with EGCG, telomerase activity was substantially reduced, dropping to approximately 50% of the baseline levels observed in the uncut controls (Fig. 1). Pharmacological inhibition of telomerase activity appeared to produce physiological consequences. Specifically, after two weeks of EGCG treatment, a decrease in the regenerative rate was observed in treated specimens compared to untreated controls,

Figure 1. Comparison of telomerase activity using the TRAP assay.

showing delayed head and foot regeneration and possibly compromised morphological integrity. By the seventh week of continued treatment, morphological abnormalities, including incomplete regeneration and cellular disorganization, began to appear.

The eventual correlation between reduced telomerase activity and decreased regenerative capacity suggests a role for telomerase in maintaining the proliferative potential of *Hydra* stem cell populations. Even in organisms lacking conventional senescence, telomerase inhibition may compromise regenerative function, raising the possibility that telomerase maintenance contributes to the exceptional longevity and regenerative properties of *H. vulgaris*. Whether the EGCG-induced impairment represents cellular senescence, as characterized in mammals, or a specific response to telomerase inhibition in this basal metazoan, and whether this association indicates direct causality or related mechanisms (e.g., telomere shortening), requires further investigation.

It should be pointed out that beyond canonical telomere lengthening, evidence in mammalian systems indicates that telomerase possesses non-canonical functions, including oxidative stress protection, maintenance of redox homeostasis, mitochondrial homeostasis, protection of mitochondrial DNA, and modulation of key signaling pathways, such as Wnt/ β -catenin and autophagy regulation [6–8]. Whether such extratelomeric functions of telomerase also operate in *Hydra* and contribute to its elevated activity during regeneration represents an intriguing question for future investigation.

Conclusion

This preliminary study demonstrates that *H. vulgaris* maintains intense telomerase activity, which is essential for sustained regeneration and apparent biological immortality. Telomerase inhibition via EGCG treatment seems to compromise regenerative capacity and induce senescence-like phenotypes, establishing a causal link between telomerase function and regenerative longevity in this model. If confirmed, these findings should clarify the fundamental mechanisms connecting telomerase activity to biological immortality in basal metazoans and provide insights into the evolutionary conservation of telomerase-dependent aging processes.

References

- Martinez, D.E. Mortality Patterns Suggest Lack of Senescence in Hydra. *Experimental Gerontology* **1998**, *33*, 217–225, doi:10.1016/S0531-5565(97)00113-7.
- Bode, H.R. Head Regeneration in *Hydra*. *Developmental Dynamics* **2003**, *226*, 225–236, doi:10.1002/dvdy.10225.
- Schmitt, H.; Blin, N.; Zankl, H.; Scherthan, H. Telomere Length Variation in Normal and Malignant Human Tissues. *Genes Chromosomes & Cancer* **1994**, *11*, 171–177, doi:10.1002/gcc.2870110306.
- Steele, R.E.; David, C.N.; Technau, U. A Genomic View of 500 Million Years of Cnidarian Evolution. *Trends in Genetics* **2011**, *27*, 7–13, doi:10.1016/j.tig.2010.10.002.
- Udroiu, I.; Russo, V.; Persichini, T.; Colasanti, M.; Sgura, A. Telomeres and Telomerase in Basal Metazoa. *Invertebrate Survival Journal* **2017**, 233–240 Pages, doi:10.25431/1824-307X/ISJ.V14I1.233-240.
- Marinaccio, J.; Micheli, E.; Udroiu, I.; Di Nottia, M.; Carozzo, R.; Baranzini, N.; Grimaldi, A.; Leone, S.; Moreno, S.; Muzzi, M.; et al. TERT Extra-Telomeric Roles: Antioxidant Activity and Mitochondrial Protection. *IJMS* **2023**, *24*, 4450, doi:10.3390/ijms24054450.
- Rosen, J.; Jakobs, P.; Ale-Agha, N.; Altschmied, J.; Haendeler, J. Non-Canonical Functions of Telomerase Reverse Transcriptase – Impact on Redox Homeostasis. *Redox Biology* **2020**, *34*, 101543, doi:10.1016/j.redox.2020.101543.
- Saretzki, G. Extra-Telomeric Functions of Human Telomerase: Cancer, Mitochondria and Oxidative Stress. *CPD* **2014**, *20*, 6386–6403, doi:10.2174/1381612820666140630095606.